

CLIMATE SUMMARY

NAME: **Alexandria**
 LOCATION: **EGY**
 DESIGN SKY: **Not Available**
 ALTITUDE: **7.0 m**
 © Weather Tool

LATITUDE: **31.2°**
 LONGITUDE: **30.0°**
 TIMEZONE: **+2.0 hrs**

